

RHEOLOGICAL STUDY OF VOLUME CONSUMPTION OF MIXTURES OF ISOBUTYLENE – ISOPRENE COPOLYMER WITH CHLORINATED POLYISOPRENE IN DIFFERENT PROPORTIONS

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Abstract

Isobutylene - isoprene, ie butyl rubber (BC) belongs to the class of saturated rubbers and is a product of copolymerization of isobutylene and isoprene. BK-based rubbers are very easy to form, have sufficient convection adhesion, high heat and ozone resistance, gas tightness and high dielectric properties. In addition to the above-mentioned positive properties, there are also disadvantages of isobutylene - isoprene rubber. For example, it has low thermoplasticity, low vulcanization rate and adhesion, inability to settle with other rubbers, etc. properties such as Butyl rubber is modified by various methods to overcome these shortcomings. For example, bromination and chlorination improve its vulcanization rate, adhesion ability, and cohesion with other rubbers. To this end, we have set as our main goal the improvement of the properties of butyl rubber by modifying it in different proportions with chlorinated polyisoprene (XPI). We first study the morphological properties of the two systems BK / XPI.

Keywords: isobutylene - isoprene, butyl rubber, modification, chlorinated polyisoprene, rheology.

1. Experimental part.

Isobutylene - isoprene is mechanically mixed with polyisoprene chlorinated in certain proportions in the laboratory for 40 minutes at a temperature of 40-50 to prepare a binary system, binary mixtures (Table 1). Volume consumption of alloys of prepared binary mixtures under pressure created by loads of 11.75 kg, 20.85 kg, 26.1 kg, 32.6 kg at temperatures of 100, 120, 150, 170 C was studied. The mixture of prepared binary mixtures in the ratio of BK / XPI - 96/4 is stored in the vulcanization system at 155 C in the chamber of IIRT-5 for 30 minutes, then it is extracted with carbon 4-chloride for 2 hours, then dried to constant weight and spectral analysis.

Infrared spectroscopic analysis of chlorinated isoprene rubber modified butyl rubber and unmodified butyl rubber was performed. Based on the obtained spectra, it is possible to suggest that the addition of chlorinated polyisoprene to butyl rubber changes the chemical

structure of the rubber. Samples for infrared spectroscopic analysis were prepared by keeping them in C on an IRT-5 device for 25 minutes. At this temperature and during this time, the chemical structure of butyl rubber modified with chlorinated polyisoprene was changed. The decrease in the intensity of the peaks in the interval corresponding to the wave number of 800 - 1700 cm and the disappearance of some peaks indicate that the double bonds in the rubber have been transformed. This claim is confirmed by the decrease and disappearance of the intensities of the combination fog and trans voltage peaks in the range corresponding to the wave number of 3100-3000 cm. With the introduction of chlorinated polyisoprene, the formation of a new chemical structure under temperature conditions is accelerated. However, the fact that the peaks of the chlorine atom are not visible in the spectrum indicates that it is below the level that can be directly determined in the composition of the mixture.

Figure 1

Figure 2

2. The result and its discussion

BK / XPI mixtures are prepared in the proportions given in the table below

(Table 1). The prepared binary mixtures were weighed in the same scale (fixed scale), placed in the chamber of the IRIT 5 device and kept for 4 minutes at

the temperature under study so that the samples take the temperature of the chamber under study. Then we record the time (in seconds) spent as a result of the effect of different loads on the flow of alloys of isobutylene isoprene and its mixtures with XPI at a certain constant distance ($s = 2\text{mm}$) from the capillary (Table 2).

Table 1.

The composition of the binary mixture

S	The code of mixture					
	Components	1S	2S	3S	4S	5S
1	BK – 2055	100	98	96	94	92
2	CHPI	-	2	4	6	8
	Sum	100	100	100	100	100

Table 2

Time spent in $s = 2\text{ mm}$ flow of alloys of BK / XPI mixtures under the influence of different temperatures and loads, in seconds.

Samples	100°C				120°C			
	loads, kg				loads, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1S	426.80	86.35	50.25	32.70	205.30	45.82	28.32	21.70
2S	432.70	97.85	58.12	40.25	210.85	48.25	32.10	22.40
3S	440.35	100.16	63.78	46.18	212.60	49.15	33.25	23.85
4S	458.25	110.24	70.65	50.10	214.18	51.65	34.75	24.90
5S	460.11	114.18	73.45	54.25	210.18	49.10	30.28	20.15
Samples	155°C				170°C			
	loads, kg				loads, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1S	132.49	31.75	17.57	11.82	118.70	42.62	17.35	12.28
2S	134.18	30.60	16.95	10.96	110.25	44.06	18.08	13.35
3S	126.75	28.15	15.05	9.08	118.18	20.12	20.12	15.65
4S	119.14	24.64	13.28	7.25	128.25	18.15	18.15	14.05
5S	110.64	20.94	12.6	6.65	120.05	16.95	16.95	12.08

After recording the flow time (t) of the alloys of isobutylene - isoprene and its mixtures with XPI in the above-mentioned technological mode from the capillary of the device IIRT-5, we calculate the volume (Q) consumption of alloys for each temperature using the following formula:

$$Q = \frac{S}{t} \times \frac{\pi D s^2}{4}$$

Here:

Q- volume consumption of the alloy, cm x sec

S - alloy flow distance, mm

t- time spent in the stream, sec

D - diameter of the cylinder of the device IIRT-5, mm

Based on the results of volume consumption calculations of alloys of isobutylene - isoprene and its mixtures with XPI for each temperature, curves depending on the amount of XPI in the volume consumption mixture are constructed.

Analyzing the results of the established graph curves, it is concluded that the decrease in volume consumption under the influence of different loads at a temperature of 100° C is due to an increase in the amount of mixed CPI. As the amount of XPI in the mixture increases, the volume consumption under the influence of all loads decreases. This means that XPI acts as a filler in the mixture and fills the gaps between the isobutylene-isoprene molecules. As a result, macromolecules reduce the oscillation because they prevent the center of gravity from moving.

Figure 3.1. Volumetric consumption of BK / XPI binary mixture at 100° C as a function of the amount of XPI in the mixture.

Beginning in the direction of increase from the second load under a temperature of 120° C, the amount of XPI in the volume consumption mixture (2-6) k.h. increases until the amount of XPI is 8 k.h. When present, XBI, which is not bound to isobutylene-isoprene

micromolecules, destructively breaks down the mixture in the mixture, and the viscosity of the mixture decreases and the volume consumption increases.

Figure 3.2.

Volume consumption of BK / XPI binary mixture at 120° C as a function of the amount of XPI in the mixture.

At a temperature of 155° C under the influence of a load of 11, 75 kg, the volume consumption of the mixture is constant, regardless of the amount of XPI in the mixture, ie there is no interaction under the influence of the specified load. Under the influence of a load of

20.85 kg, the amount of 2-4 k.h. Due to the influence of other loads (26.1 kg and 32.6 kg), the volume consumption of the mixture increases sharply, i.e the mixture is subject to the process of destruction.

Figure 3.3.

The dependence of the volume consumption in the binary mixture BK / XPI at 155⁰ C on the amount of XPI.

Under 170⁰ C temperature when XPI amount is 2 k.h in the mixture, its mixture volume decreases, i.e., structuring occurs in it and volumetric consumption increases due to destructive process in its further growth.

Figure 3.4. Dependence of volume consumption on the amount of CPI in the binary mixture BK / XPI at 170⁰ C.

Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that the vulcanization process is carried out at a temperature of 150⁰ C with a load of 20, 85 kg by mixing the mixtures obtained in a mixture of isobutylene - isoprene polymer with a concentration of 2-4 k.h. You can obtain the product by carrying it on the pressure vessel. Then IR spectral analysis of polyisobutylene - isoprene / XPI mixture was studied.

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